

Design Principles for AI-Ready Data from QCD Experiments

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Abstract

Data from large physics collider experiments in Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) research differ fundamentally from the modalities used in modern foundation models. The heterogeneity and detector dependence require principled curation for scalable AI. In this document, we present a detailed design framework for AI-ready QCD data for general-purpose physics detectors. We describe the guiding design philosophy, including data modeling choices, schema definition, and array-based representations that aim to minimize storage and computational overhead while preserving the physical information most relevant for downstream learning tasks. This framework provides an outline for applications to detectors such as the Barrel Imaging Calorimeter in the ePIC experiment at the Electron–Ion Collider.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear and particle physics detectors record particle interactions as heterogeneous electronic signals. A single collision event produces thousands of readouts across multiple subdetectors, each with distinct geometry, segmentation, readout technology, dynamic range, and noise characteristics. As a result, detector data differ fundamentally from the homogeneous arrays commonly assumed in mainstream AI workflows.

This heterogeneity makes data representation a central design problem for AI applications in QCD data. Raw detector outputs are often optimized for hardware operation, software reconstruction, or detector-specific analysis, not for large-scale AI research. Without a principled representation, AI applications become dependent on ad hoc preprocessing pipelines that are difficult to reuse across detector systems, learning tasks, and model architectures. An AI-ready format must therefore balance several competing goals: preserving physically relevant information, minimizing storage and computational overhead, and providing a consistent structure that can support scalable downstream learning.

This work defines a minimal, technology-agnostic AI-ready data format for QCD detector data. The format accommodates silicon pixel sensors, calorimeters, and waveform-based readouts within a unified schema. Two arrays form the core of the format: `measurements`, which encodes detector responses, and `labels`, which records the true physics interactions from the distinct particles that contribute to each response. This schema was also designed to be compatible with streaming readout and real-time data processing, which are becoming increasingly important in next-generation HEP and NP detectors. The physical interpretation of each field is documented in the dataset metadata, enabling use by non-experts outside the field.

II. DATA DESIGN

A. Design Principles

Detector observations are represented through a common spacetime-signal abstraction,

$$(x, y, z, A, t),$$

where (x, y, z, t) denote the coordinates associated with a measurement and A its signal amplitude. This representation is detector-agnostic. Different technologies, including silicon sensors, calorimeters, and waveform-based systems, can be expressed within the same schema once their detector-specific meanings are defined in metadata. The format follows four design principles:

1. **Unified representation.** A single schema supports all detector systems through the `detector` index and the `sample` index of hit samples, covering both single-readout and multi-sample measurements.
2. **Explicit uncertainty encoding.** Uncertainty quantifies the statistical confidence associated with the data. Spatial uncertainty is stored as the upper triangle of a 3×3 covariance matrix, while amplitude and time uncertainties are stored as scalars.
3. **Metadata-defined semantics.** Units, coordinate conventions, and detector-specific meanings are specified in metadata rather than embedded in field names.
4. **Minimal scope.** The format stores only information needed for AI applications and does not duplicate complete native event records such as HepMC3 or EDM4hep.

B. The `measurements` Array

The `measurements` array is the primary data structure for detector observations. Each row corresponds to one recorded measurement sample. Depending on the detector technology, a sample may represent a single sensor response or one element of a multi-sample readout such as a waveform. The array is designed to support heterogeneous detector systems within a single schema while preserving the information needed for downstream AI applications. Its structure is summarized in Table I.

a. Field definitions.

- **event:** Identifier for an event in physics experiment. Here, an event denotes an arbitrary grouping of measurements, such as a physics collision, a time-ordered DAQ readout, or another unit defined in the metadata.
- **detector:** Identifier for the subdetector that produced the measurement. The mapping from identifier to detector name and properties is provided in the metadata.

TABLE I. Structure of the `measurements` array.

Field	Type	Description
<code>event</code>	<code>uint64</code>	Event identifier.
<code>detector</code>	<code>uint16</code>	Subdetector identifier.
<code>hit</code>	<code>uint16</code>	Hit index within a subdetector.
<code>sample</code>	<code>uint16</code>	Sample index within a hit.
<code>x, y, z</code>	<code>float32</code> \times 3	Spatial coordinates associated with the sample.
<code>pos_cov_xx, xy, xz, yy, yz, zz</code>	<code>float32</code> \times 6	Upper triangle of the position covariance matrix.
<code>amplitude</code>	<code>float32</code>	Measured signal amplitude.
<code>amplitude_uncertainty</code>	<code>float32</code>	Uncertainty on the amplitude.
<code>time</code>	<code>float32</code>	Time associated with the measurement.
<code>time_uncertainty</code>	<code>float32</code>	Uncertainty on the time measurement.

- **hit:** Index for a distinct measurement instance within a subdetector. For example, this may correspond to a sensor hit, a channel response, or another detector-defined interaction unit.
- **sample:** Sub-index within a hit. This field provides a unified representation for both single-sample and multi-sample readouts. For single-sample measurements, `sample` is zero. For waveform-like readouts, each time sample is stored in a separate row with the same `hit` index.
- **x, y, z:** Spatial coordinates associated with the measurement. In many cases these correspond to the location of the physical readout element, since the true interaction position may require reconstruction. If clustering or other upstream processing has been applied, they may instead represent an estimated interaction position. Units and coordinate conventions are specified in the metadata.
- **pos_cov_xx, xy, xz, yy, yz, zz:** Upper triangle of the 3×3 covariance matrix associated with the spatial coordinates. This field encodes measurement resolution and correlations among spatial components.
- **amplitude:** Measured signal size. Depending on the detector, this may represent deposited energy, charge, ADC value, photoelectron count, or another detector-specific observable. Its physical interpretation and units are defined in the metadata.
- **amplitude_uncertainty:** Uncertainty associated with the stored amplitude measurement. This quantity describes the uncertainty on the recorded observable itself and

does not necessarily represent the uncertainty on a derived reconstructed quantity.

- **time:** Time associated with the measurement. This may correspond to the detector readout time or to a value assigned during upstream processing. For multi-sample readouts, per-sample times allow reconstruction of the full waveform. Units and conventions are specified in the metadata.
- **time_uncertainty:** Uncertainty associated with the stored time measurement, reflecting detector and electronics timing resolution.

III. TRUTH LABEL DESIGN

A. Design Principles

The `labels` array stores truth information associated with individual entries in the `measurements` array. Each label is defined at the measurement level, so that a recorded detector response (a measurement) can be linked directly to the particle(s) that generated the interaction being measured and are responsible for it. This design enables fine-grained detector-level truth labeling for downstream supervised learning tasks while remaining applicable across different detector technologies. The label format is guided by five principles:

1. **Measurement-level granularity.** Truth is stored per measurement rather than only per event or reconstructed object, enabling direct supervised learning at the level of recorded detector response.
2. **Top- N contributors.** For each measurement, the N contributing MC particles with the largest deposited energy are retained. This captures the dominant physical content of the signal while keeping memory usage bounded.
3. **Spatiotemporal truth description.** Each measurement label includes truth-level spatial coordinates, time, and total deposited energy, together with the corresponding quantities for each retained contributor.
4. **Particle decay chain association.** Contributor labels may be traced back to a physically relevant ancestor particle when needed by the application. For example,

in a calorimeter, this can prevent labels from being dominated by low-energy shower secondaries instead of the incident particle.

5. **Minimal information.** A limited amount of information is retained for each contributor. This is sufficient to capture common production and decay patterns without duplicating the full event-level truth record.

B. The `labels` Array

The `labels` array stores measurement-level truth labels in a tabular form aligned with the `measurements` array. Each row corresponds to one measurement and contains aggregate truth information for that measurement together with per-contributor truth fields for up to N retained particles, indexed by $n \in \{0, \dots, N - 1\}$. This structure allows a detector response to be linked both to its overall truth quantities and to the dominant particle contributions that generated it. Its structure is summarized in Table II.

TABLE II. Structure of the `labels` array, with contributor-specific fields repeated for each retained contributor $n \in \{0, \dots, N - 1\}$.

Field	Type	Description
<code>event</code>	<code>uint64</code>	Event identifier.
<code>detector</code>	<code>uint16</code>	Subdetector identifier.
<code>hit</code>	<code>uint16</code>	Hit index within a subdetector.
<code>sample</code>	<code>uint16</code>	Sample index within a hit.
<code>x, y, z</code>	<code>float32</code> \times 3	Truth spacial coordinates.
<code>energy_deposit</code>	<code>float32</code>	Truth total deposited energy.
<code>time</code>	<code>float32</code>	Truth time associated with the measurement.
<code>n_contributions</code>	<code>uint16</code>	Total number of contributing particles.
<code>con{n}_particle</code>	<code>uint32</code>	Index of contributor n in the event-level record.
<code>con{n}_x, y, z</code>	<code>float32</code> \times 3	Interaction spacial coordinate of the contributor n .
<code>con{n}_energy_deposit</code>	<code>float32</code>	Deposited energy from contributor n .
<code>con{n}_time</code>	<code>float32</code>	Time of interaction of contributor n .
<code>con{n}_px, py, pz</code>	<code>float32</code> \times 3	Momentum vector of contributor n at production.
<code>con{n}_energy</code>	<code>float32</code>	Energy of contributor n at production.
<code>con{n}_pid</code>	<code>int32</code>	PDG identifier of contributor n .
<code>con{n}_parent_pid</code>	<code>int32</code>	PDG identifier of the immediate parent of contributor n .
<code>con{n}_parent_energy</code>	<code>float32</code>	Energy of the immediate parent of contributor n .

a. Field definitions.

- `event, detector, hit, sample`: These fields mirror the corresponding identifiers in

`measurements` and allow row-level association between the two arrays. Depending on the detector and readout model, a label may correspond to a full hit or to an individual sample within a multi-sample measurement. The precise interpretation is documented in the metadata.

- **x, y, z:** Truth coordinates associated with the measurement. These represent the reference spatial location used for labeling and may correspond to a simulated interaction point, an energy-weighted position, or another detector-specific definition documented in the metadata.
- **energy_deposit:** Total deposited energy associated with the measurement, summed over all contributing particles. This field serves as the truth counterpart to the signal amplitude stored in `measurements`, although the exact relationship between the two is detector-dependent and defined in the metadata.
- **time:** Truth time associated with the measurement. In many applications this corresponds to the earliest contributing interaction time, but other definitions may be used when appropriate and should be documented in the metadata.
- **n_contributions:** Total number of distinct particle contributions associated with the measurement. Full contributor-level information is stored only for the retained top- N contributors; this field preserves the total multiplicity and therefore encodes the degree of signal overlap.
- **con{n}_particle:** Index linking contributor n to an external event-level particle truth record. The full event-level particle list is not included in this format, since widely used community standards such as HepMC3 already provide such representations. If needed, that event-level truth can be stored separately and joined through this index.
- **con{n}_x, y, z:** Truth interaction coordinates associated with contributor n . Their exact definition depends on the labeling procedure and detector response model, and is specified in the metadata.
- **con{n}_energy_deposit:** Deposited energy from contributor n within the labeled measurement.

- `con{n}_time`: Truth interaction time associated with contributor n .
- `con{n}_px`, `py`, `pz`: Production-level momentum components of contributor n , defined at the particle vertex before its interaction in the detector.
- `con{n}_energy`: Production-level energy of contributor n , defined at the particle vertex before its interaction in the detector.
- `con{n}_pid`: PDG particle identifier of contributor n .
- `con{n}_parent_pid`: PDG particle identifier of the immediate parent of contributor n . This enables limited ancestry tracing, such as identifying photons from $\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ or leptons from heavy-particle decays. The value may be set to zero when parent information is unavailable or not applicable.
- `con{n}_parent_energy`: Production-level energy of the immediate parent of contributor n . The value may be set to zero when parent information is unavailable or not applicable.

IV. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

We have presented a detector-agnostic design for AI-ready data in nuclear and particle physics, motivated by the heterogeneous structure of QCD detector readout. The proposed format is organized around two core arrays: `measurements`, which stores detector responses in a unified schema, and `labels`, which stores the corresponding measurement-level truth information from contributing particles. Together, these designs provide a compact and extensible representation that preserves physically relevant information while supporting scalable downstream AI applications.

Beyond its general utility for AI/ML applications, the curated measurement array was designed to be compatible with streaming data processing, aligning with the anticipated shift towards triggerless or streaming-style readout architectures for next-generation detector systems at the LHC and EIC. Its compact (x, y, z, A, t) structure is advantageous for such environments because it provides a uniform, low-complexity representation of detector responses while explicitly retaining time as a continuous feature for ordering, association, and real-time reconstruction.

This document also provides the AI-data design basis for a follow-up case study of the Barrel Imaging Calorimeter (BIC) in the ePIC detector at the future Electron–Ion Collider. The BIC is a hybrid electromagnetic calorimeter that combines AstroPix silicon pixel imaging layers with Pb/ScFi calorimeter layers, making it an ideal system for testing a unified AI-ready data format. Its readout spans both single-sample pixel measurements and multi-sample waveform signals, directly exercising the heterogeneous representation developed here. Its broad granularity and detector coverage make it a strong benchmark for both data design and downstream AI applications. For these reasons, the BIC in ePIC will provide a compelling first demonstration of the general framework introduced in this work. In addition, as BIC is itself pursuing streaming-capable readout, this design choice also helps demonstrate that the proposed representation is practical for such detector systems and compatible with anticipated future triggerless data acquisition and processing modes.

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